

AN OVERVIEW OF INTERCULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

In recent years we as teachers are expected to prepare our students for the challenges of the 21st century, as we are aware of many changes taking place globally. Population movement continues to occur throughout the world, bringing about cross-cultural contact between groups who speak different languages and carry different cultures. Forecasts focus on an increasingly interconnected world through global travel and international communications that are instant and available to more and more people. Businesses and professions require employees who speak more than one foreign language fluently, to participate in the international labor market as well as to serve the ethnolinguistic minorities who come and grow. This change, affects not only sectors of society, industry, health, politics or business, but also education. In various parts of Europe as elsewhere in the world, school curriculum designers include intercultural objectives in school curricula and teachers find themselves faced with the challenge of promoting and supporting the acquisition of intercultural competence through teaching. This is true for teachers of various subjects, but mostly for those of foreign languages. Foreign language teaching is cross-cultural in nature. Introducing the foreign language into a classroom means connecting students to a world that is different from their own.

Keywords: foreign language, intercultural competence, international communication, education.

Introduction

The dynamics of globalization have brought about changes in the concept of learning foreign languages: learning one or several languages is no longer (or not only) an ascertainable fact of this or that individual, otherwise called cultured, but a professional obligation that is related to the exercise of different professions. Technology development as well as the growth of cultural, economic and political exchanges has made linguists and professionals talk about specialized communication as well as learning a foreign language for specific purposes. People feel the need to learn many foreign languages to exchange technical and professional experiences, to be informed at any moment, to adapt to different situations where different activities take place.

The views of Wilhelm von Humboldt²⁸ had a great influence on the development of many areas in linguistics. According to the scientist, "the division of humanity into peoples and tribes and the change in its languages and dialects are closely related and depend on a third phenomenon of a higher order - the action of the human spiritual force, which always appears in new and often the most perfect forms ... Each specific language is associated with a spiritual people. With all the thinnest threads of its roots, it has grown together ... with the strength of the national spirit and the stronger it is the influence of the spirit on the language, the more natural and richer is the development of the latter." The spirit of men and the language of men are inseparable: "The spiritual peculiarity and the structure of the language of men are in such close fusion with each other so that as soon as one exists, then another must flow

from it ... Language is, so to speak, an external manifestation of the soul of nations: the language of the people is its spirit, and the spirit of the people is the language theirs, and it is difficult to imagine anything more identical"²⁹

Ideas of intercultural communication have attracted more and more attention in the field of education.

In the 1960s the subject "Intercultural Communication" was taught in a number of American universities. In the 1970s the purely practical nature of the course was supplemented by the necessary theoretical generalizations and took the form of a classic university course, combining both theoretical provisions and practical aspects of intercultural communication.

In Europe, the formation of intercultural communication as an academic discipline developed somewhat later than in the United States. In some European universities at the turn of the 70-80s of the twentieth century, intercultural communication departments were opened (Munich, Jena).

In Munich, curricula for intercultural communication were developed, based on materials from folklore, ethnology and linguistics.

According to Spolsky (2004), "Language-management efforts may go beyond or contradict the set of beliefs and values that underlie a community's use of a language and the actual practice of language use" (p. 14);

In the last ten years, new professions have appeared. Logically, this has led to the spread of new special language practices oriented towards professional

²⁸ Humboldt. On Language, On the Diversity of Human Language Construction and its Influence on the Mental Development of the Human Species. Edited by Michael Losonsky, CUP 1999,

needs. These ideas are an expression of what Richterich³⁰ first called "partial competence": "Today no one aims for a complete ability to communicate in a foreign language, to practice it like a native". This is also observed in students who have defined goals and therefore the main value of teaching and learning is usefulness.

The general trend in Europe is to give foreign languages an ever greater place and importance than before and this is related to the growing social demands for languages.

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Multilingualism is one of the basic principles of language policies in Europe. This is one of the reasons that the Council of Europe and the European Union have drawn up the "Common European Framework of Reference for Languages", the basic document to which all European educational institutions refer. On the basis of this document, all Higher Education institutions in Europe have built their plans and teaching programs for foreign languages, achieving a transparency and measurement of the real level of students' knowledge. This document is the main tool for creating a compact within the education system.

At the same time, there is a mismatch between the general needs of the political-social, economic-social system and the specific needs of young people, between the formation and obtaining of a tool. So there are contradictions between the social demand, the possibilities of the institution and issues related to the peculiarities of the subject. In fact, each actor tries to defend his position in the social field, pursues his objectives without worrying about the real conditions in which a language can be explained or taught in school. Although public opinion has serious doubts about the validity of the school system in the field of language teaching, society expects the school to overcome this challenge.

At the center of a professionally oriented foreign language training is often a double problem: a student who is not a language specialist, but who has good reference knowledge of his field of activity and manages the conceptual instruments used, is faced with a specialist pedagogue of language and didactics but who has limited knowledge of the student's field of activity and does not manage the conceptual instruments very well. The ESP (English for Specific Purposes) teacher, who has to weave together the learning objectives and the needs of the students according to a personal view of the specialist area of his audience, generally faces great difficulties. Moreover, ascertaining the many parameters that must be taken into account (needs, student profile, level of language skills, training context, training objectives, etc.), presents difficulties in the field in terms of developing programs.

The last point we want to address in our overview is that of the cultural dimension of communication. Often, the methods present recipes and advice to follow during contact rituals and are mainly interested in the

linguistic translation of cultural codes (use of the second person plural, linguistic forms appropriate to the context) limiting themselves to these aspects.

For us and our experience in the field, it confirms that the recognition of the other, and the opposite, is done through confronting the stereotypes of the students towards those representatives of the marked culture, from a reflection on the multiplicity of communication and on the codes that define it in a culture of determined by a questionnaire on the mechanisms of interculturalization. Sensitizing students to this notion is of fundamental importance for the public of professionals, who encounter many problems thanks to their ethnocentric reflexes in foreign professional contexts.

As products of social interaction, linguistic activities are materialized and organized in texts, thus becoming part of time and space, that is, part of a productivity context. The text has a close connection with its context of creation and also carries characteristics such as: the way of organizing its content, the pronunciation of sentences connected to each other, the presence of mechanisms of textuality and expressive load. The speaker of any language must be able to distinguish these, whether in the mother tongue or in a foreign language. Learning a foreign language would be envisaged, in this perspective, as the development of the ability to understand and produce different types of texts in a foreign language, according to situations of linguistic interaction. The same applies to professional language teaching.

This inventory of linguistic interaction situations belonging to the professional field in question and the description of their linguistic forms can be done through a classification of text types, organized in the form of a didactic sequence, with the aim of developing a community of linguistic skills of the student.

We think that in learning a professional foreign language, we can focus (but not only) on the analysis of texts as well as on the realization of projects related to the profession where discourse and professional skills can be combined. For example, in the field of tourism there are specialists who deal with the drafting of guides (brochures) or advertisements in foreign languages for Albania. These specialists find it necessary to study the features of written texts in the field of tourism. Other specialists need direct oral communication with the foreign tourist or in writing via the Internet. So, the conception of a formation based only on the discourse analysis of written texts would be truncated.

Authentic writings in the field of tourism are among the most diverse: advertisements, catalogs of tourist agencies, guides, brochures.

The difference between a General Foreign Language program and a language program in a specialized field can be said to lie in the selection of language interaction situations, which may be more general in the first case and more closely related to the specific contexts defined by the professional field in question in the second case. This choice must be made in function of the needs that D. Lehmann emphasizes, not only linguistic needs, but also cultural needs and professional

³⁰ Richterich, R. (ed.) Case studies in identifying language needs. Oxford (1983).

skills, without which any educational program risks being incomplete. Educators who teach foreign languages in different faculties must do their continuous research to perfect themselves in teaching foreign languages in this field, i.e. self-education. This does not mean that they become specialists in the field because the goal is not to explain the specialty in a foreign language, but to equip students with language knowledge to express themselves in their profession in the future. Some of the ways for independent training can be:

- reading specialty books or magazines,
- cooperation with pedagogues of this specialty or with specialists in this field

The sources of materials for its formation today are quite rich. The Internet, written or visual media, specialized books, radio conversations, etc., constitute a rich inventory of materials to be used by teachers. Through the Internet, he can establish contacts with foreign pedagogues and exchange experiences and pedagogical materials.

Communication is an important aspect of it and as a facilitator of the learning process based on human values and a regulator of relations between social groups and the school microenvironment. Pedagogical - educational communication in the broadest sense is like a special form of discourse characterized by the places of social interaction where it takes place. The new profile of classroom communication is important because it allows us to make a more in-depth analysis of aspects of teaching. According to the new concept, the teacher is less of a teacher and more of an administrator who organizes the school environment so that the child discovers his "self", discovers the other, discovers the environment and is constantly engaged in exploratory activities. Through various activities, each child uses and develops his physical, artistic, social and intellectual abilities.

The well-known American psycholinguist R. Jakobson³¹ classifies communication functions in this way.

- The referential function – where we refer to an object in the world around us while talking.
- Emotive function - the case when communication causes emotions in others.
- The injunctive function - affirmative, negative, commanding, inhibiting messages are emitted during this communication.
- Aesthetic function – interlocutors give color and intonation to their conversation, eloquence, etc. - Factual function – includes the deformations of the professional field as well as the use during communication

with uncontrolled and worthless expressions like good, good or not, i.e. **Conclusion**

In conclusion, we can say that for the construction of the foreign language program for professional purposes, the following stages can be followed:

- Analysis of the professional context;
- Determination of personnel;
- Needs analysis;
- Study of communication situations that students will face in their profession;
- Data collection;
- recordings of concrete oral communication situations and the collection of specialty written materials.
- Data analysis and their adaptation to the communicative objectives of teaching:
- discourse analysis.
- the evidence of lexical-syntactic features, linguistic structures, cultural elements as well as the mode of operation and the most prominent types of discourse.

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³¹ Jakobson. R. "Fundamentals of language" s-Gravenhage : Mouton (1956)